

**IMPORTANT ISSUES OF PROTECTING THE PROPERTY RIGHTS OF
BUSINESS ENTITIES TO LAND PLOTS**

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Abstract. The thesis examines the importance of protecting the property rights of business entities to land plots, problems in practice, their impact on the country's reputation in international rankings, improving the legislation on the protection of property rights in order to develop entrepreneurship and ensure the welfare of the people.

Key words: private property, guarantees of the rights of owners, compensation, international ratings, protection of property rights to land plots, improvement of legislation.

Nowadays, developed countries are making progress in ensuring the inviolability of private property and protecting property rights. In particular, according to the report of the International Economic Freedom Ranking 2023, which includes the "Right to Property" indicator, Singapore (83.9 points), Switzerland (83.8 points) and Ireland (82.0 points) ranked the first 3 places¹, they have achieved the country's economic development and people's welfare by ensuring the reliable protection of property rights and business environment. Therefore, when implementing political, economic, social and legal reforms, it is necessary to study property relations regarding to land from a scientific, theoretical and practical point of view, and strengthen the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of owners.

¹ https://www.heritage.org/index/pdf/2021/book/2021_IndexofEconomicFreedom_Highlights.pdf

The protection of property rights, as well as other human rights, is guaranteed by international legal instruments, in particular Conventions, Pacts and other international legal documents. The protection of property rights is reflected in Article 17 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which is considered as the most important international human rights instrument, and paragraph 1 of this Article states that “Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others”. Paragraph 2 provides that “No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property”. In addition, it should be noted that the International pact on “Economic, social and cultural rights” focuses on the issue of property rights of individuals. According to the Fifth Amendment to the U.S. Constitution (1791), no person shall be deprived of life, liberty, or property without due process of law. Private property shall not be taken for public use without just compensation².

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing systematic measures to reliably protect the inviolability of property rights, increase the level of capitalization of private property, ensure the stability of property and legal relations to the land, and guarantee the property rights of landowners. In particular, it has been determined that land plots will be allocated to the private sector on the basis of ownership and lease rights, non-agricultural land will be sold through electronic Internet auctions on the basis of ownership and lease rights, and the powers of local self-government bodies to make a decision or other type of document in relation to the land plots are revoked, thus it has been established that documents that are the basis for the emergence of the right to land plots shall be annulled only in a judicial procedure.

Nevertheless, the law enforcement practice shows that the enforcement of documents on the inviolability of property rights is not fully ensured. It should be noted that the seizure of land plots for public needs, as well as the demolition of objects located on the seized land plot, is a problem in many countries, and the lack

² <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Russian-translation-U.S.-Bill-of-Rights.pdf>

of proper legal regulation of these issues leads to violations of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens and business entities. In particular, in the period before the approval of the new procedure for confiscation of land plots and provision of compensation to real estate owners, conflict situations arose in various regions of Uzbekistan, which negatively affected the country's reputation in the international arena. For example, in 2018-2019, there was no clear list of what exactly is called the need of the state and society. Therefore, there were cases when a land plot was taken away from businessman A and given to businessman B³.

As a result of violations of property rights in the country, Uzbekistan's place in the "Property Rights" indicator of the "Economic Freedom" index maintained by the Heritage Foundation research center was observed. In 2021 Uzbekistan was on the 75th place in the ranking. In 2022, on this indicator it dropped 73 places to 148th out of 180 countries. According to the report of this world ranking for 2023⁴, Singapore (83.9 points), Switzerland (83.8 points) and Ireland (82.0 points)⁵ took the first 3 places, while Uzbekistan scored 56.5 points out of 100, ranked 109th⁶ among 184 countries on this indicator. "The country's property rights ranking is lower than the world average⁷," the report said.

Furthermore, in the report for 2022, Uzbekistan is ranked 138th out of 140 countries where property rights are not guaranteed in the subindicator "The government does not confiscate property without a court order and fair compensation" of The World Justice Project (WJP) Rule of Law Index⁸. International rankings place property rights below the world average as one of the

³ <https://daryo.uz/k/2022/08/10/yer-uchastkalari-noqonuniy-ravishda-olib-qo%25ca%25bbyilgan-taqdirda-mansabdor-shaxslarga-bhmning-100-baravaridan-200-baravarigacha-bo%25ca%25bblgan-miqdorda-jarima-solinadi/k/k/rss>

⁴ The report is based on a database for the period July 1, 2021 through June 30, 2022.

⁵ https://www.heritage.org/index/pdf/2021/book/2021_IndexofEconomicFreedom_Highlights.pdf

⁶ <https://www.heritage.org/index/country/uzbekistan>

⁷ <https://www.heritage.org/index/country/uzbekistan>

⁸ https://worldjusticeproject.org/rule-of-law-index/downloads/INDEX_2022-digital.pdf

obstacles limiting basic economic freedom, and recommend important reforms in this regard⁹.

In view of these circumstances, the constitutional guarantees of private property were strengthened and the Law "On the procedure for the withdrawal of land plots for State needs" on June 29, 2022 was adopted.

Therefore, the following objectives need to be addressed in the study:

➤ to define the concept and content of property rights of business entities to land plots, to analyze the criteria related to land ownership rights from the point of view of new legal policy and legislation;

➤ to conduct a comparative study and analysis of legal norms regulating the protection of property rights of business entities to land plots;

➤ analyze the peculiarities of protecting the property rights of business entities to land plots;

➤ to analyze the legislation and judicial practice on the issues of protection of the rights of business entities during the withdrawal of land plots for state needs;

➤ to study the problems of recognizing the rights to unauthorized land plots and buildings constructed on them, analyze ways to solve them and develop proposals;

➤ to identify problems of protecting the property rights of business entities to land plots and development of proposals and recommendations for their elimination.

In civil law, land as an object of property rights has a special feature, and in modern jurisprudence, the protection of property rights of business entities to land plots is considered one of the new institutions to be studied, and although the legal framework has been formed, the norms governing these relations have not been fully developed. Therefore, it is advisable to analyze the criteria related to land ownership rights from the point of view of new legal policy and legislation, to

⁹ “Иқтисодий эркинлик индекси 2023” эълон қилинди // <https://www.imv.uz/oz/news/category/yangiliklar/post-1060>

improve the legislation on the protection of ownership rights to land plots by developing scientifically substantiated proposals.

In particular, it should be taken into account that the property rights of business entities to land plots are understood as their rights to land plots, permanent use (possession), lease, temporary use, as well as limited use of another person's land plot (servitude).

The inconsistency of norms of the Civil and Land Codes regarding land ownership rights and elimination of legal gaps are also topical issues.

According to the above, the following proposals are put forward as a result of the study:

The new version of the Constitution enshrines the inviolability of private property, the owner cannot be deprived of his property except in cases and in the manner prescribed by law and not based on a court decision, the value of the house for the owner is deprived of the home and the place of harm in cases and in the manner prescribed by law, on prior and equal compensation, the need to determine the norms regarding the possibility of finding land in private ownership under conditions and procedures that ensure its rational use;

To strengthen at the legislative level the procedures for withdrawal of land plots for public needs in exchange for compensation, to establish a clear and complete list of cases in which land plots may be withdrawn for public needs, to decide on the confiscation of land plots and to demolish real estate located on the confiscated land plot, determining the procedure in accordance with the interests of the owners, not allowing the demolition of real estate until compensation is paid to the right holder, decision of the Jokorgy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakistan;

It is substantiated that in case of disputes on the right of ownership, use or lease of land, it can be canceled only by court decision, strengthening the rights and legitimate interests of owners in the withdrawal of land for state and public

needs, the inviolability of private property that arose in the process of expropriation, and the results of expropriation are justified;

It is based on the fact that the determination of ownership rights to a land plot, the complete abolition of the authority of local self-government bodies to make decisions on the allocation and withdrawal of land, the consequences of unauthorized occupation of land plots, the documents of the Soviets of People's Deputies, including the possibility of appealing in court against the decision to confiscate a land plot;

The development of a new draft law "On the Protection of Private Property and Guarantees of Owners' Rights" is based on the fact that documents that are the basis for the emergence of the right to land plots are recognized as invalid only by the court;

It is substantiated that the decision to demolish real estate objects located on an alienated land plot should be made only in the presence of a positive conclusion of the judicial authorities and the agreement concluded between the administration and the right holder, providing for the amount, type and term of compensation should be notarized;

In order to ensure reliable protection of the rights of owners, it is necessary to strengthen liability for deprivation of property and property rights without a court decision, as well as to establish criminal and administrative liability for illegal seizure of a land plot. reasonable;

The need to develop a draft decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the application of legal norms and ensuring uniform judicial practice when considering land disputes in courts.